

A global catalogue of spatiotemporal drought events derived from multivariate hydrological data

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ABSTRACT

We present a global catalogue of spatiotemporally clustered drought events spanning 1980–2024, identified using a three-dimensional implementation of the DBSCAN algorithm. The catalogue is based on daily data using four hydroclimatic variables: precipitation, potential evapotranspiration, soil moisture, and surface runoff. Drought conditions were consistently defined using a 10th percentile threshold, enabling detection of meteorological, agricultural, and hydrological drought types. Each drought event is represented as a three-dimensional cluster in space and time, and includes detailed metadata on spatial extent, temporal duration, severity, and centroid evolution. This structure enables systematic analysis of global drought dynamics and compound extremes. The dataset is openly available at <https://zenodo.org/records/17581124>, providing a reusable resource for climate, hydrology, and hazard research. Annual updates will be released to extend the database, ensuring the catalogue remains a living resource for climate, hydrology, and risk-assessment research.

Background & Summary

Droughts are dynamic, multivariate phenomena that evolve across space and time. While traditional assessments often rely on single-variable indices, such as precipitation anomalies, more advanced indices combine multiple variables to better capture drought conditions. Additionally, traditional applications of multivariate indices usually describe droughts as temporally isolated anomalies within single grid cells or catchments, or as long-term spatial statistics, rather than capturing their full spatiotemporal development.

To address this gap, we developed a global catalogue of spatiotemporal drought clusters derived from four hydroclimatic variables, soil moisture, runoff, precipitation, and potential evapotranspiration, at 0.5° spatial resolution and daily timestep from 1980 to 2024. Drought conditions were consistently defined for each variable by using a locally varying 10th-percentile threshold (calculated for each grid cell and day of the year), a widely applied criterion in both operational and research contexts that allows cross-variable comparability^{1,2}.

Recent methodological advances have made it possible to overcome many limitations of traditional drought assessments. Early soil-moisture-based studies^{3,4} demonstrated the value of physically based modeling for capturing drought intensity and duration. Building on this foundation, clustering and tracking algorithms now enable droughts to be analyzed as evolving spatiotemporal events^{5,6}. Approaches such as centroid tracking and ST-DBSCAN have been used to follow drought migration and quantify displacement^{6,7}, while 3D DBSCAN has been applied for event detection using precipitation and temperature anomalies^{8–11}. In parallel, other studies based on gridded drought indices rather than clustering algorithms have highlighted increasing drought severity and multiyear persistence at the global scale^{12–15}. Closely related studies also applied OPTICS clustering to soil moisture anomalies, but these were limited to a single variable¹⁶. Our catalogue incorporates multiple drought types simultaneously and applies a uniform clustering framework to generate coherent, event-based records at the global scale.

The resulting dataset provides a comprehensive resource for drought attribution studies, hydrological assessments, and machine-learning workflows aimed at hazard monitoring and compound event analysis. By cataloguing events across space and

39 time, it enables systematic exploration of drought dynamics at regional to global scales. In addition, the catalogue can be used
40 to evaluate trends in drought frequency and persistence, to examine how drought development relates to large-scale climate
41 modes, and to train or validate machine-learning models for early detection and hazard monitoring.

42 **Methods**

43 **Input Data**

44 The dataset combines meteorological reanalysis with hydrological model simulations. Precipitation and surface (2-m) air
45 temperature were obtained from the ERA5 global reanalysis¹⁷, while soil moisture and runoff were simulated with the
46 mesoscale Hydrologic Model (mHM), a distributed, process-based hydrologic model that uses multiscale parameter
47 regionalization to obtain effective at the scale of interest and simulate key water-cycle components. In mHM the water balance
48 is closed at every grid cell, and all major hydrologic fluxes and state variables are calculated for each cell individually^{18,19}. Soil
49 moisture represents the average water content over the full 2 m root-zone profile. Runoff is taken as surface runoff,
50 corresponding to the direct overland flow component simulated at the grid-cell scale. Potential evapotranspiration was
51 estimated using the Hargreaves–Samani method²⁰ based on ERA5 temperature variables. All datasets were aggregated to a
52 common 0.5° grid to provide a uniform analysis framework. Aggregating all datasets to a common 0.5° grid ensured a uniform
53 analysis framework, resulting in globally consistent hydroclimatic fields at daily resolution for 1980–2024.

54 **Drought Event Identification**

55 Drought conditions were identified independently for each variable. To reduce high-frequency variability, precipitation was
56 smoothed with a 30-day moving average, a well-established method in hydrological and drought research^{21,22}. Soil moisture
57 *state variable* reflects longer-term water storage conditions in the root zone, making its percentile deficit directly interpretable
58 as a measure of agricultural and hydrological drought stress. The standardized anomalies of precipitation, PET, and runoff
59 *fluxes* instead capture short-term meteorological forcing and surface response^{18,19}.

60 Soil moisture deficits were identified using percentile thresholds computed from long-term daily climatology, with a 30-day
61 smoothing window applied to reduce variability. Specifically, the 10th percentile of daily soil moisture (1980–2024) was used
62 as a dynamic threshold for each grid cell and calendar day. Daily values below this threshold were expressed as relative
63 deviations:

$$\text{def}(t) = \frac{SM(t) - SM_{p10}(d)}{SM_{p10}(d)} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

64 where $SM(t)$ is the simulated soil moisture on day t and $SM_{p10}(d)$ is the daily 10th-percentile climatology for day-of-year d .
65 Values falling below this threshold were interpreted as drought conditions, while values above it were not considered part of a
66 deficit. The resulting index represents the percentage shortfall of root-zone soil water relative to the lower decile of expected
67 conditions. This percentile-based approach is conceptually consistent with previous mHM-based drought studies^{19,23,24},
68 although here it is applied at daily resolution and using day-of-year specific percentiles, rather than monthly standardized
69 indices. Using a percentile threshold also follows operational drought monitoring practice, where drought severity is defined
70 relative to local climatology (e.g., U.S. Drought Monitor¹; Intersucho²⁵), ensuring interpretability across climate regions.
71 For precipitation, potential evapotranspiration, and runoff, anomalies were standardized to z-scores over the 1980–2024
72 baseline to ensure comparability across regions and variables. Z-scores were calculated by subtracting the long-term mean from
73 each value and dividing by the standard deviation. The standardization was performed independently for each calendar month.
74 Drought conditions were then defined as days where the standardized anomaly fell below the grid-cell specific 10th percentile
75 of the z-score distribution. Unlike SPI^{26,27} or SPEI²⁸, which require fitting probability distributions to estimate standardized
76 drought indices, the z-score approach provides a simpler, distribution-free representation of anomalies^{1,29}. Although z-scores
77 are less sensitive to short dry spells, they remain widely used in global drought assessments and comparative analyses across
78 climate regimes^{1,29,30}. Next, we applied a custom “deficit volume calculation function” that flags all days where the
79 standardized anomaly falls below the 10th-percentile drought threshold and groups consecutive deficit days into continuous
80 events. Short interruptions and short events are adjusted according to the control parameters described below:

- 81 • **mit** (*minimum inter-event time*): the allowable number of consecutive non-deficit days that may occur within a larger
82 deficit period without breaking the event. This accounts for brief fluctuations such as isolated rainfall that do not
83 interrupt the drought’s persistence.
- 84 • **min.len** (*minimum length*): the shortest duration a continuous (corrected) deficit period must have to be classified as a
85 drought event. This ensures that only sustained dry periods are retained.

86 Figure 1 illustrates the effect of *mit* and *min.len* parameters on detected drought event. In the top panel (*mit* = 0, *min.len* = 4),
87 short interruptions break up the sequence of deficits, so only longer continuous periods are classified as drought events. In

88 contrast, the bottom panel ($mit = 5$, $min.len = 1$) allows brief non-deficit days and accepts shorter durations, resulting in longer
89 and more frequent drought events being identified. Each identified drought event was characterized by its duration and intensity
90 (cumulative deficit), enabling spatiotemporal tracking in subsequent clustering. Computation of thresholds and anomalies relied
91 primarily on Climate Data Operators (CDO)³¹, which efficiently handle large NetCDF files (tens of GB in this project). All
92 further analyses, including 3D DBSCAN clustering, were performed in R³².

93 **Spatiotemporal Clustering via 3D DBSCAN**

94 We identified drought events as connected regions in space and time using a 3D DBSCAN algorithm^{5,33,34}. Each input pixel
95 was represented by its spatial coordinates (latitude/longitude), temporal index, and severity weight (that is, the z-score of the
96 deficit from the deficit from the previous time step). Clustering was performed in two steps: (i) a spatial DBSCAN applied to
97 each time step, followed by (ii) a full 3D DBSCAN across space and time.

98 The parameterization of DBSCAN followed the approach of Cammalleri et al.³³ with settings chosen to balance event detection
99 and noise suppression (Table 1). Key parameters include:

- 100 • **Neighborhood size:** the smallest meaningful spatial ($s_{xy} = 3$) and temporal ($s_t = 3$) windows, limiting the risk of
101 merging adjacent but unrelated events and enabling detection of small, localized droughts.
- 102 • **Core point density:** a fractional minimum number of points ($fr_{mP} = 0.25$) within the search window, ensuring
103 compact, well-defined clusters.
- 104 • **Minimum cluster size:** a filter of $c_{min} = 50$ pixels ($\approx 125\,000\text{ km}^2$ on the equator for the resolution of 0.5 degree) to
105 exclude spurious or fragmented regions.
- 106 • **Intensity weighting:** the parameter w_{lim} (with $w_{exp} = 1.5$) was varied to adjust the influence of drought severity. This
107 allowed for the prioritization of impactful events when the number of clusters became too large for cataloguing.

108 The influence of these parameters on event detection is illustrated in Figure 2, which shows how 3D DBSCAN derives clusters
109 from soil moisture deficits over South America on March 3, 2011. Increasing c_{min} removes smaller clusters, while increasing
110 w_{lim} gives more weight to pixels with larger z-score deficits, making them more likely to be included in clusters. A higher
111 s_{xy} value enlarges the search radius, allowing more neighboring deficit pixels to be grouped into the same cluster.

112 All the clustering analyses were implemented using the `dbscan()` function from the R package **dbscan**³⁵. To process large
113 datasets efficiently, clustering was parallelized in R using the **parallel**³², **doSNOW**³⁶, and **foreach**³⁷. Each thread accessed
114 NetCDF input files independently via **ncdf4**³⁸. After temporal stacking of pixel-level drought flags, a final 3D DBSCAN pass
115 assigned a unique cluster ID to each drought pixel and recorded its spatial position, time step, and weighted drought severity.

116 **Postprocessing**

117 After the 3D DBSCAN clustering, each pixel belonging to a specific drought event was assigned a cluster ID together with its
118 spatial location, temporal index, and weighted drought intensity. A postprocessing workflow then aggregated these pixel-level
119 assignments into comprehensive event-level metadata describing the spatial extent, duration, severity, and evolution of each
120 cluster. To focus on persistent events, we retained only clusters lasting at least 30 days (10 days for potential evapotranspiration,
121 where higher threshold would otherwise exclude most events). For each cluster, the following attributes were derived:

- 122 • **Event-level attributes:** start and end dates, total duration, pixel count, and median spatial/temporal centroids.
- 123 • **Evolution attributes:** daily centroid position, daily cluster area (km^2), cumulative severity, and minimum/maximum
124 extent.
- 125 • **Movement attributes:** centroid displacement calculated with the Vincenty's formulae, azimuth of movement (using
126 rhumb line), and cardinal direction of movement (N, NE, E, etc.).

127
128 The resulting clusters and derived attributes were exported as global NetCDF files and corresponding R catalogue tables for
129 each variable, as described in the following section.

130 **Data Records**

131 The complete dataset is publicly available at Zenodo [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17581124]. It consists of two complementary
132 components for each of the four analyzed variables—precipitation (PRE), potential evapotranspiration (PET), runoff (Q) and
133 soil moisture (SM):

- 134 • **NetCDF files:** Four global gridded files that store the 3D DBSCAN cluster identification for each variable at 0.5° spatial
135 and daily temporal resolution (1980–2024) named:

- 136 – PRE_ERA5_3Ddbscan_global_res0p5_1980_2024_1day.nc
- 137 – PET_ERA5_3Ddbscan_global_res0p5_1980_2024_1day.nc
- 138 – Q_mHM_3Ddbscan_global_res0p5_1980_2024_1day.nc
- 139 – SM_mHM_3Ddbscan_global_res0p5_1980_2024_1day.nc

140 Each file provides, for every grid cell and day, the integer cluster identifier corresponding to the drought event detected at
141 that location and time.

142 • **R catalogue tables:** Two accompanying R data files (.rds) per variable that summarize cluster characteristics in tabular
143 form:

- 144 – summary_<var>.rds — one record per drought event, describing overall event-level properties.
- 145 – stats_<var>.rds — daily time-step records for each event.

146 The parameters contained in these files are detailed in Table 2.

147 Together, the NetCDF maps and R catalogue tables form a coherent global drought-event database and provide a robust
148 foundation for downstream analyses of drought evolution, size, severity, and spatial dynamics across variables and time. In
149 total, the dataset includes 4315 precipitation, 1724 potential-evapotranspiration, 813 runoff and 715 soil-moisture clusters.
150 These differences reflect the distinct response times of the variables, where precipitation and PET exhibit high short-term
151 variability, while soil moisture and runoff integrate conditions over longer periods, resulting in fewer but generally more
152 persistent events. Heatmaps of cluster occurrence are shown in Figure 3, illustrating the spatial patterns and frequency of
153 identified drought events across variables. Precipitation clusters, unlike the other variables, were derived also over oceans, with
154 pronounced hotspots in the tropics and high latitudes. Potential evapotranspiration clusters show strong activity over eastern
155 Europe and central Asia, as well as marked hotspots in South America and southern Africa. Soil moisture clusters are more
156 spatially confined, with concentrations primarily in South America and central Africa. Runoff clusters display a broader
157 distribution, occurring relatively evenly across the higher latitudes of the Northern Hemisphere, while also recurring
158 prominently in South America and central Africa.

159 Technical Validation

160 To ensure the robustness of the catalogue, we conducted several checks focusing on both the deficit calculation procedure and
161 the clustering methodology.

162 We evaluated how the identification of drought events responds to the configuration of the deficit volume algorithm, particularly
163 the minimum inter-event time (*mit*) and minimum length (*min.len*) parameters. Figure 1 illustrates how varying these
164 parameters influences event detection by allowing short interruptions or filtering out very short anomalies. Based on sensitivity
165 testing supported by visual inspection of event time series, the selected parameter combination preserves persistent drought
166 periods while preventing artificial fragmentation or inclusion of short events.

167 Since density-based clustering algorithms are inherently sensitive to parameter settings, we performed experiments with
168 multiple values of the 3D DBSCAN parameters, focusing on the spatial neighborhood size (s_{xy}) and the intensity weighting
169 threshold (w_{lim}). We tested configurations using both daily and 10-day temporal resolutions to examine the stability of the
170 resulting drought clusters. The experiments showed that while absolute numbers and sizes of events vary with parameter
171 choice, large-scale spatiotemporal drought patterns remained consistent, supporting the robustness of the catalogue across
172 parameterizations. Representative examples of parameter effects are shown in Figure 2.

173 Finally, we compared our soil moisture drought clusters with the independent global catalogue of Řehoř et al.¹⁶, which applied
174 the OPTICS algorithm to the same underlying data. The two datasets show similar spatial hotspot patterns (e.g., across South
175 America and central Africa) and comparable timing of major multi-year drought periods, despite differences in clustering
176 methodology. This qualitative correspondence indicates that the identified events reflect robust large-scale drought dynamics
177 rather than methodological artifacts.

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184 Author contributions statement

185 **VŠ:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Software, Formal Analysis, Validation, Visualisation, Writing – Original Draft
186 Preparation.

187 **OR, MH:** Conceptualisation, Software, Validation, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Writing - Review & Editing

188 **CC:** Software, Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing

189 **VM:** Methodology, Validation, Writing - Review & Editing

190 **RK, YM, JŘ, MT:** Conceptualisation & Review

191 Competing interests

192 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

193 References

- 194 1. Svoboda, M. D., Fuchs, B. A. *et al.* *Handbook of drought indicators and indices*, vol. 2 (World Meteorological
195 Organization Geneva, Switzerland, 2016).
- 196 2. Kuleshov, Y., Kurino, T., Kubota, T., Tashima, T. & Xie, P. Wmo space-based weather and climate extremes monitoring
197 demonstration project (sem dp): first outcomes of regional cooperation on drought and heavy precipitation monitoring for
198 australia and southeast asia. In *Rainfall-extremes, distribution and properties* (IntechOpen, 2019).
- 199 3. Samaniego, L., Kumar, R. & Zink, M. Implications of parameter uncertainty on soil moisture drought analysis in germany.
200 *J. Hydrometeorol.* **14**, 47–68 (2013).
- 201 4. Andreadis, K. M., Clark, E. A., Wood, A. W., Hamlet, A. F. & Lettenmaier, D. P. Twentieth-century drought in the
202 conterminous united states. *J. Hydrometeorol.* **6**, 985–1001 (2005).
- 203 5. Lloyd-Hughes, B. A spatio-temporal structure-based approach to drought characterisation. *Int. J. Climatol.* **32**, 406–418
204 (2012).
- 205 6. Diaz, V., Perez, G. A. C., Van Lanen, H. A., Solomatine, D. & Varouchakis, E. A. An approach to characterise
206 spatio-temporal drought dynamics. *Adv. Water Resour.* **137**, 103512 (2020).
- 207 7. Sabut, A., Mishra, A. & Entekhabi, D. Spatiotemporal patterns of drought migration across the contiguous united states.
208 *Water Resour. Res.* **61**, e2024WR039855 (2025).
- 209 8. Liu, Z. & Zhou, W. Glo3dhydroclimateeventset (v1. 0): A global-scale event set of hydroclimatic extremes detected with the
210 3d dbscan-based workflow (1951–2022). *Int. J. Climatol.* **43**, 7722–7744 (2023).
- 211 9. Liu, Z. & Zhou, W. Global seasonal-scale meteorological droughts. part i: Detection, metrics, and inland/coastal types.
212 *Ocean. Res.* **2**, 0016 (2023).
- 213 10. Liu, Z. & Zhou, W. Global seasonal-scale meteorological droughts. part ii: temperature anomaly-based classifications.
214 *Ocean. Res.* **2**, 0017 (2023).
- 215 11. Liu, Z., Zhou, W. & Wang, X. Extreme meteorological drought events over china (1951–2022): Migration patterns,
216 diversity of temperature extremes, and decadal variations. *Adv. Atmospheric Sci.* **41**, 2313–2336 (2024).
- 217 12. Chen, H., Wang, S., Zhu, J. & Wang, D. Projected changes in the pattern of spatially compounding drought and pluvial
218 events over eastern china under a warming climate. *Earth's Futur.* **11**, e2022EF003397 (2023).
- 219 13. Chen, L. *et al.* Global increase in the occurrence and impact of multiyear droughts. *Science* **387**, 278–284 (2025).
- 220 14. Gebrechorkos, S. H. *et al.* Global high-resolution drought indices for 1981–2022. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data Discuss.* **2023**,
221 1–28 (2023).
- 222 15. Gebrechorkos, S. H. *et al.* Warming accelerates global drought severity. *Nature* 1–8 (2025).
- 223 16. Řehoř, J. *et al.* Global catalog of soil moisture droughts over the past four decades. *EGUsphere* **2024**, 1–34 (2024).
- 224 17. Hersbach, H. *et al.* The era5 global reanalysis. *Q. journal royal meteorological society* **146**, 1999–2049 (2020).
- 225 18. Kumar, R., Samaniego, L. & Attinger, S. Implications of distributed hydrologic model parameterization on water fluxes at
226 multiple scales and locations. *Water Resour. Res.* **49**, 360–379 (2013).
- 227 19. Samaniego, L., Kumar, R. & Attinger, S. Multiscale parameter regionalization of a grid-based hydrologic model at the
228 mesoscale. *Water Resour. Res.* **46** (2010).

- 229 **20.** Hargreaves, G. H. & Samani, Z. A. Reference crop evapotranspiration from temperature. *Appl. engineering agriculture* **1**,
230 96–99 (1985).
- 231 **21.** Van Loon, A. F. & Van Lanen, H. A. A process-based typology of hydrological drought. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* **16**,
232 1915–1946 (2012).
- 233 **22.** Beyene, B., Van Loon, A., Van Lanen, H. & Torfs, P. Investigation of variable threshold level approaches for hydrological
234 drought identification. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci. Discuss.* **11**, 12765–12797 (2014).
- 235 **23.** Samaniego, L. *et al.* Anthropogenic warming exacerbates european soil moisture droughts. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* **8**, 421–426
236 (2018).
- 237 **24.** Rakovec, O. *et al.* The 2018–2020 multi-year drought sets a new benchmark in europe. *Earth’s Futur.* **10**, e2021EF002394
238 (2022).
- 239 **25.** Trnka, M. *et al.* Drought monitor for the czech republic-*www.intersucho.cz. MENDEL AND BIOCLIMATOLOGY*
240 630–638 (2014).
- 241 **26.** McKee, T. B., Doesken, N. J., Kleist, J. *et al.* The relationship of drought frequency and duration to time scales. In
242 *Proceedings of the 8th Conference on Applied Climatology*, vol. 17, 179–183 (California, 1993).
- 243 **27.** Edwards, D. C. Characteristics of 20th century drought in the united states at multiple time scales. Tech. Rep. (1997).
- 244 **28.** Vicente-Serrano, S. M., Beguería, S. & López-Moreno, J. I. A multiscalar drought index sensitive to global warming: the
245 standardized precipitation evapotranspiration index. *J. climate* **23**, 1696–1718 (2010).
- 246 **29.** Dogan, S., Berktaş, A. & Singh, V. P. Comparison of multi-monthly rainfall-based drought severity indices, with
247 application to semi-arid konya closed basin, turkey. *J. Hydrol.* **470**, 255–268 (2012).
- 248 **30.** Patel, N., Chopra, P. & Dadhwal, V. Analyzing spatial patterns of meteorological drought using standardized precipitation
249 index. *Meteorol. Appl. A journal forecasting, practical applications, training techniques modelling* **14**, 329–336 (2007).
- 250 **31.** Schulzweida, U. Cdo user guide, [10.5281/zenodo.10020800](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10020800) (2023).
- 251 **32.** Team, R. C. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna,
252 Austria (2022).
- 253 **33.** Cammalleri, C. & Toreti, A. A generalized density-based algorithm for the spatiotemporal tracking of drought events. *J.*
254 *Hydrometeorol.* **24**, 537–548 (2023).
- 255 **34.** Ester, M., Kriegel, H.-P., Sander, J., Xu, X. *et al.* A density-based algorithm for discovering clusters in large spatial
256 databases with noise. In *kdd*, vol. 96, 226–231 (1996).
- 257 **35.** Hahsler, M., Piekenbrock, M. & Doran, D. dbscan: Fast density-based clustering with r. *J. Stat. Softw.* **91**, 1–30,
258 [10.18637/jss.v091.i01](https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v091.i01) (2019).
- 259 **36.** Corporation, M. & Weston, S. *doSNOW: Foreach Parallel Adaptor for the 'snow' Package* (2022). R package version
260 1.0.20.
- 261 **37.** Microsoft & Weston, S. *foreach: Provides Foreach Looping Construct* (2022). R package version 1.5.2.
- 262 **38.** Pierce, D. *ncdf4: Interface to Unidata netCDF (Version 4 or Earlier) Format Data Files* (2023). R package version 1.21.

Table 1. 3D DBSCAN Parameters Description

Parameter	Description
s_xy	Spatial neighborhood size in grid cells, forming a window centered on each pixel.
eps_xy	Spatial distance threshold used in DBSCAN, computed as the Euclidean distance across the s_xy kernel. Controls spatial proximity.
s_t	Size of the temporal window (in days) for 3D clustering.
eps_t	Temporal distance threshold used in 3D clustering, set equal to eps_xy for onsistent scaling across space and time.
fr_mP	Fraction used to compute the minimum number of points (minPts) required to form a dense region. Applied to the number of potential neighbors in the search window in both 2D and 3D steps.
mP_xy	Minimum number of spatial neighbors in 2D required to form a cluster. Derived from fr_mP and s_xy.
mP_t	Minimum number of points in 3D (space–time) required to form a cluster. Derived from fr_mP, s_xy, and s_t.
c_min	Minimum number of pixels for retaining 2D clusters before performing full 3D clustering. Helps filter out small or fragmented regions.
w_lim	Controls the intensity threshold for weighting drought magnitude.
w_exp	Controls the steepness of the weight response to drought intensity.
www	Weight assigned to each pixel using the defined weight function. Derived from input deficit value and conversely from w_lim and w_exp.

Table 2. Description of the variables contained in the stats_<var>.rds and summary_<var>.rds files.

summary_<var>.rds	
Parameter	Description
cluster_id	Unique identifier of the drought event (matches stats_<var>.rds).
start_index	First time step of the cluster (integer index).
end_index	Last time step of the cluster (integer index).
duration_days	Total cluster duration in days (or timesteps).
pixel_count	Total number of pixels that belong to the cluster across its full duration.
lat_cen	Median latitude of the cluster centroid (degrees).
lon_cen	Median longitude of the cluster centroid (degrees).
severity_total	Sum of drought intensity (weighted deficit volume) over the entire cluster lifetime.
area_max_km2	Maximum spatial area of the cluster (km ²) across all time steps.
area_min_km2	Minimum spatial area of the cluster (km ²) across all time steps.
stats_<var>.rds	
Parameter	Description
cluster_id	Unique cluster identifier (integer).
time_index	Time step index (integer).
lon_median	Median longitude of all cluster pixels (degrees).
lat_median	Median latitude of all cluster pixels (degrees).
area_km2	Area of the cluster at this time step (square kilometers).
severity	Sum of drought intensity (weighted deficit volume) across all pixels at this time step.
dist_km	Distance traveled by the cluster centroid since previous time step (kilometers).
azimuth_deg	Bearing of centroid displacement since previous time step (degrees, 0° = north, clockwise).
direction	Cardinal direction of centroid movement (e.g., N, NE, E, ...).

Figure 1. Effect of *mit* and *min.len* parameters on detected drought events. Bars represent standardized anomalies (z-scores) over time. Red columns denote periods classified as drought events according to the applied *mit* (minimum inter-event time), *min.len* (minimum event length) settings and selected threshold, while grey columns indicate non-event periods.

Figure 2. The effect of varying the minimum cluster size (c_{min}), intensity threshold for weighting drought magnitude (w_{lim}), and spatial neighborhood radius (s_{xy}) on drought event detection. Colored areas show clusters identified by 3D DBSCAN, overlaid on z-score deficits from 13.03.2011 over South America. Parameter settings strongly influence the size, extent, and continuity of detected clusters.

Figure 3. Spatial distribution of relative cluster occurrence for each variable (1980-2024). Maps show the relative frequency with which each grid cell was part of a spatiotemporal drought cluster, normalized to the maximum hotspot for each variable (0 = no cluster occurrence, 1 = highest occurrence). Results are presented for runoff, soil moisture, potential evapotranspiration, and precipitation over the period 1980–2024. Darker colors highlight regions that repeatedly contributed to drought clusters relative to other areas.